

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns

df = pd.read_csv(r"D:\DataScience Projects\amazon_prime_titles.csv")
```

Data Preprocessing

Head

```
# head - head is used to show the top 5 elements by default
# but we are able to define the number are rows to show
df.head(2)
```

show_id	type	title	director
0	s1	Movie The Grand Seduction	Don McKellar
1	s2	Movie Take Care Good Night	Girish Joshi

date_added	cast	country
0	Brendan Gleeson, Taylor Kitsch, Gordon Pinsent	Canada
1	Mahesh Manjrekar, Abhay Mahajan, Sachin Khedekar	India

release_year	rating	duration	listed_in
0	2014	NaN	113 min
1	2018	13+	110 min

description	
0	A small fishing village must procure a local d...
1	A Metro Family decides to fight a Cyber Crimin...

Tail

```
#.tail() - is used to show the last rows
df.tail(2)
```

show_id	type	title	director
9666	s9667	TV Show Maradona: Blessed Dream	NaN
9667	s9668	Movie Harry Brown	Daniel Barber

date_added	cast	country

```

9666 Esteban Recagno, Ezequiel Stremiz, Luciano Vit... NaN
NaN
9667 Michael Caine, Emily Mortimer, Joseph Gilgun, ... NaN
NaN

      release_year rating duration listed_in \
9666          2021  TV-MA  1 Season      Drama, Sports
9667          2010     R   103 min Action, Drama, Suspense

                                description
9666 The series tells the story of Diego Maradona, ...
9667 Harry Brown, starring two-time Academy Award w...

```

Shape

```

# shape - shows the number of rows and columns in the data set
df.shape

(9668, 12)

```

Columns

```

# Columns - is used for knowing the columns of the data set
df.columns

Index(['show_id', 'type', 'title', 'director', 'cast', 'country',
      'date_added',
      'release_year', 'rating', 'duration', 'listed_in',
      'description'],
      dtype='object')

```

dtypes

```

#.dtypes - used to know the datatype of each column
df.dtypes

show_id      object
type         object
title        object
director     object
cast         object
country      object
date_added   object
release_year int64
rating       object

```

```
duration      object
listed_in     object
description   object
dtype: object
```

unique

In a column, It shows the unique value of specific column

```
df["director"].unique()
array(['Don McKellar', 'Girish Joshi', 'Josh Webber', ...,
      'John-Paul Davidson, Stephen Warbeck', 'Emily Skye',
      'Steve Barker'], dtype=object)
```

nunique

It will show the total number of unique value from whole data frame

```
df.nunique()
show_id      9668
type         2
title        9668
director     5773
cast         7927
country      86
date_added   84
release_year 100
rating       24
duration     219
listed_in    518
description  9414
dtype: int64
```

describe

describe() is used to showcase the mean, standard deviation, count etc...

```
df.describe()
           release_year
count  9668.000000
```

```

mean    2008.341849
std     18.922482
min     1920.000000
25%    2007.000000
50%    2016.000000
75%    2019.000000
max     2021.000000

```

#.value_counts It shows all the unique values with their count

```

df["director"].value_counts()

director
Mark Knight          113
Cannis Holder        61
Moonbug Entertainment  37
Jay Chapman         34
Arthur van Merwijk   30
...
Karyn Kusama         1
K. Subash            1
Robert Cuffley       1
J. Sabarish         1
Steve Barker         1
Name: count, Length: 5773, dtype: int64

```

isnull

it shows the null values

```

df.isnull()

   show_id  type  title  director  cast  country  date_added  \
0     False  False  False    False  False   False     False
1     False  False  False    False  False   False     False
2     False  False  False    False  False   False     False
3     False  False  False    False  False   False     False
4     False  False  False    False  False   False     False
...      ...   ...   ...      ...   ...   ...       ...
9663  False  False  False    False  False   True      True
9664  False  False  False    True   False   True      True
9665  False  False  False    False  False   True      True
9666  False  False  False    True   False   True      True
9667  False  False  False    False  False   True      True

   release_year  rating  duration  listed_in  description
0             False    True     False     False     False

```

```
1      False  False  False  False  False  False
2      False  True   False  False  False  False
3      False  True   False  False  False  False
4      False  True   False  False  False  False
...
9663   False  False  False  False  False  False
9664   False  False  False  False  False  False
9665   False  False  False  False  False  False
9666   False  False  False  False  False  False
9667   False  False  False  False  False  False
```

```
[9668 rows x 12 columns]
```

Task 1

How many Null Value present , Show all the null values using heatmap

```
sns.heatmap(df.isnull())
```

```
<Axes: >
```


Task 2

In which Year Highest Number of TV shows and movies were released

```
df['release_year'].value_counts()
```

```
release_year
2021    1442
2020     962
2019     929
2018     623
2017     562
...
1922         2
1926         2
```

```
1924      1
1923      1
1927      1
Name: count, Length: 100, dtype: int64
```

Task 3

How many Movies and Tv shows are in the dataset

```
df.type.value_counts()
type
Movie      7814
TV Show    1854
Name: count, dtype: int64

df['type'].value_counts()
type
Movie      7814
TV Show    1854
Name: count, dtype: int64

movie_keys = list(df[df['type'] == 'Movie'].type)
tv_keys = list(df[df['type'] == 'TV Show'].type)

df.type.value_counts().plot(kind = 'pie')
<Axes: ylabel='count'>
```



```
df.type.value_counts().plot(kind = 'bar')
```

```
<Axes: xlabel='type'>
```


Task 4:

show all the records with type "movies" & country is "United Kingdom"

```
df[(df["type"] == 'Movie') & (df["country"] == "United Kingdom")].head(3)
```

show_id	type	title	director	cast	country
4	s5	Monster Maker	Giles Foster		
5	s6	Living With Dinosaurs	Paul Weiland		
14	s15	Elon Musk: The Real Life Iron Man	Sonia Anderson		

```

\
4 Harry Dean Stanton, Kieran O'Brien, George Cos... United Kingdom
5 Gregory Chisholm, Juliet Stevenson, Brian Hens... United Kingdom
14 Elon Musk, Per Wimmer, Julie Anderson-Ankenbra... United Kingdom

   date_added  release_year  rating  duration  listed_in  \
4  March 30, 2021      1989    NaN    45 min  Drama, Fantasy
5  March 30, 2021      1989    NaN    52 min  Fantasy, Kids
14   May 2, 2021      2018    NaN    74 min  Documentary

                                     description
4  Teenage Matt Banting wants to work with a famo...
5  The story unfolds in a an English seaside town...
14 Discover the meteoric rise of Elon Musk, the m...

```

Task 5

Show top 3 directors . who gave the highest number of tv shows and movies released on prime video

```
df["director"].value_counts().head(3)
```

```

director
Mark Knight      113
Cannis Holder    61
Moonbug Entertainment  37
Name: count, dtype: int64

```